

A Burton-Miller isogeometric boundary element method: Application in airport noise mapping

João Pedro de Marchi Oliveira*, Sérgio Gustavo Ferreira Cordeiro†

XXIX Encontro de Iniciação Científica do ITA – XXVII ENCITA/2024

Abstract

Noise mapping is an important aspect of airport design and requires exterior acoustic analysis. This work presents an isogeometric boundary element method (IGBEM) for acoustic analysis, which adopts independent bases for the geometric description of the problem and for the approximation of the unknown boundary fields. The IGBEM was applied to solve the Burton-Miller Boundary Integral Equation (BIE), which is required for a stable formulation of exterior acoustic problems. The method was validated by calculating the radiation from a circular cylinder, which has a known analytical solution, and finally, an application regarding the acoustic radiation from a simplified airplane is presented for illustrative purposes.

Palavras-chave: Aeroacoustics. Burton-Miller Formulation. IGBEM.

1 Introdução

Aircraft traffic is a profoundly irritating factor for people who live near airports. Exterior acoustic analysis allows the investigation of noise pollution in these areas (BRANCATI, 2010). The isogeometric boundary element method (IGBEM) is a new numerical method which provides a seamless design-analysis integration and is well-suited for dealing with infinite domains such as those in exterior acoustic problems (SIMPSON et al., 2014; BEER; MARUSSIG; DUENSER, 2020). The objective of the present work is to develop, in the Julia language, an IGBEM code to solve exterior acoustic problems. Validation and application examples are also presented.

2 IGBEM for exterior acoustic problems

Exterior acoustic problems are problems governed by the acoustics equations, and defined over infinite domains, such as Ω_∞ , illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Exterior problem (SIMPSON et al., 2014).

2.1 Governing equations of linear acoustics

Assuming time-harmonic wave motion, the governing equation of linear acoustics can be studied in terms of the velocity potential $u(\mathbf{x})$, resulting in the Helmholtz equation

$$\nabla^2 u(\mathbf{x}) + k^2 u(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_\infty, \quad (1)$$

where $k = \omega/c$ is the wave number, ω is the angular frequency of the time-harmonic wave and c is the speed of sound. Equation 1 can be converted into a well-posed Boundary Integral Equation (BIE) known as the Burton-Miller boundary integral equation (BURTON; MILLER, 1971). The solution of acoustic problems requires solving this BIE over Ω_∞ , subject to the appropriate boundary conditions and, for exterior problems, the radiation condition at infinity.

2.2 IGBEM for solving the Burton-Miller BIE

The boundary Γ of the exterior problems can be described as union of curves: $\Gamma_u = \bigcup_{e=1}^{N_u} \Gamma_u^e$ and $\Gamma_q = \bigcup_{e=1}^{N_q} \Gamma_q^e$, where $u(\mathbf{x})$ is known in Γ_u and $q(\mathbf{x})$ is known in Γ_q . The problem's geometry is described using a NURBS parametrization and the chosen basis for the unknown fields are B-splines. It is possible to obtain, from the collocation method applied to the Burton-Miller BIE, the following system of equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_u & -\mathbf{G}_u \\ \mathbf{H}_q & -\mathbf{G}_q \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \mathbf{q} \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_u \\ \mathbf{f}_q \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Solving Eq. 2, it is possible to obtain the coefficients u_i and q_i of the boundary fields approximations. Accurate solutions for the velocity potential $u(\mathbf{x})$ at interior points $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_\infty$ can be computed by recalling the Burton-Miller BIE.

*Aeronautics Institute of Technology, tipo de vínculo (aluno pesquisador voluntário), joao.marchi@ga.ita.br.

†Aeronautics Institute of Technology, tipo de vínculo (professor), sergio.cordeiro@gpita.br.

3 Results

The validation of the method is done herein by solving two exterior problems of acoustic radiation.

3.1 Acoustic radiation from a cylinder

The cylinder investigated in this example has a radius of 1.0 and has a velocity $q = \partial u / \partial n = 1$ throughout its boundary (in some consistent but unspecified units). The analytical solution for this problem is reported in Yoon, Park e Eversman (1990). Figure 2 shows the comparisons between the analytical solution and the Helmholtz and Burton-Miller IGBEM numerical solutions obtained for the velocity potential norm $|u|$ using 12 B-splines basis functions of order 2, considering different wave numbers.

Figure 2 – Wave number vs velocity potential norm.

Notice that the Helmholtz IGBEM solution resulted in significant spurious errors for wave numbers around $k = 5.52$. The Burton-Miller IGBEM solution on the other hand does not suffer from such spurious responses, as expected (BURTON; MILLER, 1971).

3.2 Acoustic radiation from an airplane

In order to illustrate the problem of acoustic radiation from an airplane, a unity value of q_2 was assigned to represent the noise generated in the fuselage, while $q_1 = 5q_2$ was prescribed to represent the noise produced by the engines. The problem's geometry is represented using 24 NURBS curves (TEIXEIRA, 2023). This configuration is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Acoustic radiation from an airplane.

The acoustic pressure $p(\mathbf{x}) = -i\rho\omega u(\mathbf{x})$ is calculated for the material and frequency input values are deliberately set to 1 and the geometry of the airplane. The boundary fields u are approximated by B-splines of order 3, which resulted in 72 collocation points. Figure 4 illustrates $|p|$ in a finite region of the domain.

Figure 4 – Acoustic pressure results.

Such acoustic pressure maps are used to build zone maps of noise.

4 Concluding remarks

In this work, an IGBEM code which adopts independent bases for the geometric description and boundary fields approximations was developed. The method was applied to solve exterior acoustic problems and was validated by calculating the acoustic radiation from a circular cylinder, which demonstrated the well-posedness of the Burton-Miller formulation. To show a possible application of the method, the acoustic radiation from an airplane was also presented.

Bibliography

- BEER, G.; MARUSSIG, B.; DUENSER, C. *The isogeometric boundary element method*. 1. ed. Stuttgart: Springer, 2020. Acesso em: 25 jul 2024.
- BRANCATI, A. *Boundary Element Method for Fast Solution of Acoustic Problems: Active and Passive Noise Control*. Tese (Doutorado) — Imperial College London, london, england, 2010. Acesso em: 25 jul. 2024.
- BURTON, A.; MILLER, G. The application of integral equation methods to the numerical solution of some exterior boundary-value problems. *Proceedings of the Royal Society: A*, v. 323, p. 201–210, 1971.
- SIMPSON, R. et al. Acoustic isogeometric boundary element analysis. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, v. 269, p. 265–290, 2014.
- TEIXEIRA, G. H. *An independent basis isogeometric boundary element formulation*. Dissertação (Mestrado) — Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica, São José dos Campos, Brazil, jul. 2023. Acesso em: 25 jul. 2024.
- YOON, W.; PARK, J.; EVERSMA, W. Two-dimensional radiation and scattering at short wave length. *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics*, v. 112, p. 384–391, 1990.